

The neutral zone approach for rehabilitation of significantly atrophied residual ridge – A functional approach to denture stability.

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Abstract

Retention, stability, and support are the main goals of the entire denture, and they depend on several variables. The most crucial of these are the surface area of the tissue that wears the denture and the strength of the surrounding muscles. The stability of the dentures is hampered by the increased resorption of the lower edentulous ridge caused by long-term edentulism.

Complete dentures are made using the neutral zone procedure, especially for people who are edentulous and heavily resorbed. It focuses on positioning denture teeth and forming the denture base so that the muscles of lips, muscle of cheek and tongue muscles work in harmony. Region of oral cavity that known as the "neutral zone" is where these opposing muscle groups apply the denture with the least amount of disruptive force, improving stability, retention, and patient comfort.

This article presents complete denture fabrication for a significantly atrophied mandibular residual ridge by recording neutral zone.

Keywords: Complete denture, Denture stability, Neutral zone, Resorbed ridges.

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Introduction

Restoring the form, function, and aesthetics of individuals who are fully or partially edentulous, is the main objective of advanced dentistry. The stability of a complete denture depends on the interaction between the teeth and the alveolar ridge. Because of outward shift of the crest of residual ridge, the tooth position might not be appropriate for extremely resorbed ridges, even though it may be preferred when there is availability of sufficient alveolar ridge height.^[1]

As patients age increases, ridge resorption also increases in edentulous patients. Greater ridge resorption results in a smaller denture base area, which lowers the stability with decreased retention. To solve this issue, dentures can be

fabricated with functional contours to mimic neutral zone.^[2]

Neutral zone is defined as potential space between the lips and cheeks on one side and the tongue on the other, that area or position where the forces between the tongue and cheeks or lips are equal.^[3]

Fish (1931) originally explained how polished surfaces affect stability and retention. Additionally, he explained how complete dentures can be fabricated in the "neutral zone".^[4]

Bates referred to it as the "Reciprocal zone," "Zone of minimum conflict," by Mathew, "Zone of neutral muscular forces" by Fenn, Heath as the "Denture space," Robert as the "Potential space," and Russell as the "Reciprocal space".^[5]

This article's goal is to demonstrate how recording of the neutral zone can be used to fabricate dentures over a significantly atrophied ridge that have better stability and function.

Case Report:

A male patient of 68 yrs of age came to our Department of Prosthodontics at Haldia Institute of Dental Sciences and Research. His complaint was that he has difficulty in chewing food, speech and poor aesthetics.

On examination, we found that both the maxillary and mandibular ridges were fully edentulous with significantly resorbed mandibular ridge (Figure 1). The patient had a period of edentulousness for the last 7 years.

The decision was made to create a complete denture utilizing the neutral zone technique.

Primary impressions of edentulous arches were taken with modelling compound.

Special trays were made with cold cure acrylic resin. Wash impressions were obtained with ZOE impression paste (Figure 2).

Master cast was obtained. Acrylic base plates & wax rims were fabricated.

Wax rims were adjusted and Jaw relations were recorded.

On the mandibular master cast, another baseplate was fabricated, and a 22-gauge orthodontic wire loop was made. These loops were used to adhere the admixed impression material for neutral zone recording (Figure 3).

A mixture ratio of 7 parts impression material and 3 parts green stick material was utilized to capture the neutral zone. Admix material was softened in warm water of 65^o C and loaded onto the record base with loops and placed it intraorally.

Patient was instructed to do puckering, smiling, wide mouth opening, wetting the upper and lower lips, whistling, and loudly speaking the words 'A, E and O' to record the neutral area (Figure 4).

The addition silicone putty index was made for this neutral zone record (Figure 5), and the

mixed material was taken out from the record base, and the arrangement of the teeth was accomplished using the putty index as a reference

Try-in of waxed denture was done and checked for esthetics, speech and bilateral occlusion (Figure 6).

Flasking, dewaxing, packing, curing, finishing, polishing was done conventionally. Denture insertion was done (Figure 7 and 8).

Patient was briefly given post insertion instructions and recalled next day for follow-up. Regular check-up was done in 3-month interval till 12 months.

Discussion:

Pound showed that as a result of resorption, the maxillary residual ridge shifts towards lingual direction and the mandibular residual ridge shifts towards buccal direction.^[6]

According to Atwood^[7], the factors that affect resorption rate are

- Anatomic,
- Metabolic,
- Functional,
- Prosthetic.

The movement of muscles that surrounds the complete denture is not static; it is dynamic.

The record that is obtained by the neutral zone technique is specific to the patient. Its position specific width, are reproducible.

A complete denture fabricated with a neutral zone approach improves the stability between the oral and perioral musculatures.^[8] It also decreases food entrapment, improves aesthetics, and better aligns the posterior teeth, allowing tongue space.^[9]

The teeth arrangement by following the neutral zone has two main aims:

- (1) Natural muscle activity without interference of artificial tooth.
- (2) Forces by natural perioral and intraoral muscle that acts upon denture, supports & maintains the denture.

The influence of neuromuscular action on lower complete dentures was documented in this article. The method described here details the fabrication of a complete denture which does not affect neuromuscular activity to achieve functional contours and neutral position of artificial tooth.

Conclusion:

This case report points out an innovative way for treating a fully edentulous patient with significantly resorbed ridges, notably the mandibular ridge. The neutral zone approach being amongst the best approaches for significantly atrophied residual ridges, its application is uncommon due to its intricacy and additional clinical steps. Neutral zone recording is a rapid, accurate, non-invasive, and cost-effective method. To enhance the stability of the denture and improve patient satisfaction and treatment outcomes, this technique can potentially be combined with other procedures.

Considering the advantages of neutral zone technique, clinicians should apply it in their day to day practice for managing edentulous patients.

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FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8